

THE ROLE OF DRESSES IN THE LIFE OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: This article tells about the history of the national costumes of the Uzbek people, which reflect the identity of our people along with their nationality and show their ethnic signs. The study of national costumes, like other areas of folk marriage, is closely related to the application of the ethnic history and culture of each people, its interactions with other peoples. It is also a criterion that reflects the national identity of peoples within material and spiritual monuments and indicates ethnic signs. In this sense, the study of the history of the robe gives a large overview of the rich cultural heritage of the peoples who have lived on the Earth for several thousand years, and at the same time their traditions, their way of living. Dresses not only satisfy the natural and aesthetic needs of people, but at the same time they contain traditions of each nation, social relations, some elements of ideology, religious beliefs, sophistication and aesthetic norms. In addition, Clothes Show the place and time in which a person lived, his imagination, joyful or sad events. Clothing is a component of the material and spiritual culture of society. On the one hand, it has a certain material value as a product of human labor, satisfying certain ir needs, on the other hand, it is also called an example of Applied-decorative art. Like structures, weapons of Labor and such unique tools, the dress also provides information about a certain historical period, the natural climatic conditions of the country, the national identities of the people and its vision of beauty. While the concepts of clothing and dress seem to be in essence shared with each other, there are also some differences between these concepts. Clothing or clothing refers, first of all, to items that are necessary to cover different parts of the human body, protecting it from various influences of the external environment. There are several types of dresses: women's dresses, men's dresses, wedding and ceremonial dresses, tops, clothes with various ornaments, etc. All these objects, together with accessories, decorations, hairstyles that perform various tasks, form the concept of a common dress. It is the dress that shows the social origin of a person, his distinctive features, age, gender, character and aesthetic taste. Some researchers have explained the reasons for the appearance of clothing in different

ways. In fact, when did the dress appear? What reason did humanity need him? These and similar questions should be of interest to many. In this article you will get answers to several similar questions.

Key words: the concept of clothing and dress, the history of the dress, ethnic signs, dresses from different regions of Uzbekistan, the sign of nationality.

Dresses appeared in the most ancient periods of human development 40-25 thousand years ago. Shoes, on the other hand, appeared only in later times, and are somewhat more common than other elements of the dress. A dress is not only a means of providing a natural need, but at the same time it is also an example of Applied Art. Like all examples of Applied Art, it is characterized by beauty as well as orientation towards a specific purpose. In addition to carrying out the practical task of keeping the body from various external influences, in particular, from heat and cold, it also has aesthetic functions, such as decoration, beauty. Therefore, as society progresses, as the aesthetic taste of people increases, the emphasis on the decoration of clothes, the main thing is not to repeat. For example: in historical costumes, the decoration of the allowance meant the social origin, that is, the class of its owner, and also represented the aesthetic taste of people, as well as acquiring a figurative meaning. Dresses have improved over time, species have increased, and forms have become more complex. Each person used different decorations in the decoration of his dress. Thus, the complexity of the appearance of forms and ornaments on dresses is influenced by historical factors - external environment, climate, seasons, etc.; socio-economic factors – historical progress, ethnicity, religion, lifestyle, development of Science and techniques, human factor, psychology, etc. In this sense, the stages of development of each people leave their mark on the costumes of the people. This pattern also suggests that the robes change to match the period and style. This article presents information about the history of the formation and development of the costumes of the Uzbek people. Dresses from different regions of Uzbekistan differ from each other. In this sense, Uzbek dresses are studied in 4 regions: Tashkent-Fergana dresses, Bukhara-Samarkand dresses, Kashkadarya-Surkhandarya dresses and Khwarezm dresses.

In Tashkent and the Fergana Valley, traditional national clothing represented the social status of different categories of the population. The clothes in these provinces were characterized by their presence of quiet colors. Black and Green were

used more often in the clothes of the Fergana Valley and Tashkent. In the national costumes of Bukhara and Samarkand, the cultural influence of neighboring states is observed, the main forms and some elements of which have been created for centuries. In our mamalakat, in the XIX centuries, many banoras, beqasam, adras, silk silk fabrics, wonderful abreast fabrics were very popular. The ABR fabrics of Bukhara used mainly - dark red, yellow and pink. The National clothes of Bukhara and Samarkand are distinguished from the clothes of other regions of Uzbekistan by their lush appearance and unique Zoroastrian embroidery.

Kashkadarya and surkhandarya Oasis are located in southern Uzbekistan. They are characterized by the warmth of their climate, due to natural conditions, the national clothing of the inhabitants of the country was also suitable for nature Shariah. Bright colors of clothes, free physique and unique, varied embroidery indicate the high taste of people. Surkhandarya clothes clearly express the centuries-old ideas of traditional and artistic creativity of the ancestors, and women's headdresses, called "wearers", "heads", are unique to the same Surkhandarya and are not found in other regions of Uzbekistan. The women of this region liked red, cherry colors, but at the same time they were very fond of jewelry. And the national costumes of kashkadarya are distinguished by contrasting colors: bright red, orange, dark brown, purple, green. In kashkadarya and Shahrisabz, the "Iraqi" method of embroidery is common. In Khorezm, the art of minting, making ornaments and making jewelry is very developed. Unlike other regions, Khwarazm is distinguished by the variety and complexity of its forms of ornaments. The men's headdress chopper from time immemorial is also very popular.

Today, many Europeanized garments are becoming more common through the modernisation of Uzbek national costumes. It is true that this is due to the clothes that young people are promoting. To prevent this, it is necessary to increase the show of more doppelgängers, satin and adras dresses. While Uzbek national costumes have undergone changes, traditionalism can be said to have not left us also. In place of the conclusion, it should be said that national dress designs are becoming more and more sophisticated these days. They now penetrate deeply into the layers of traditional ethnic culture, positively mastering the achievements of other cultures. The design of each dress under development has its own morphology and social, historical significance. Modern dizany is directly related to the materialization of culture, which in itself reflects the teran processes of various exchanges taking place in society, the

manifestations of a diverse universe, such as national, social, scientific and artistic. In our national costumes are embodied many features of the thousand-century history, traditions, ancient traditions, aesthetic views and spiritual tastes of our people, as well as their own. Our national costumes reflect ibo, hayo and nationalism, which are characteristic of the Uzbek people. We can promote our nationality on world stages without hesitation.

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